

FORMATION OF INFORMATION COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS USING MODERN ELECTRONIC MEANS

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Annotation. *This article provides a definition of information competence, the importance of modern computer programs in the development of information competence of students, components and criteria of information competence, indicators for measuring and determining the level of information competence. Also in the article, the computer network model creator Arena-Rockwell, ExtendSim-Imagine Than Inc, Anylogic-XJ Technologies, NetMaker XA, Opnet-OPNET Technologies, Cisco Packet Tracer modern programs about briefly stopping the past.*

Key words: *information competence, information and communication technologies, electronic educational resources, computer programs, distance education sites.*

INTRODUCTION. The modern information society is characterized by the comprehensive use of the powerful potential of information and communication technologies, the creation of a single global information space that provides wide access to information and the production of various information resources. The goal of training students in the higher education system is to prepare highly qualified and competitive personnel with the ability to effectively use information and communication technologies in their specialty. The tasks of the modern education system are not to give students as much knowledge as possible, but to teach them to choose what they need from a large amount of information, to prepare intellectually developed creative individuals, and to attract their personal abilities to various fields of activity. independent activity based on information disclosure.

For students Many scientists V.V.Grishkun [2], S.G.Grigoriev [2], O.U.Gogitsaeva [3], G.S.Kubanseva [1] conduct scientific research on the formation of information competence. In their work, they studied the formation of information competence of higher school students as a new literacy, its content, the use of

information and communication technologies, independent search for information, processing and making the necessary decisions, as well as standard and non-standard computer skills, including modeling skills using cases.

LITERARY ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY. Information competence – reflects the ability to search, analyze, select, process and transmit the necessary information, regardless of oral and written information using information technology [5]. The formation of information competence begins in secondary school and continues in higher education. To increase the level of information competence in the information society, a person must first of all systematize the information and knowledge received and highlight what is really important to him. It is necessary to manage the flow of diverse information, identify and select the known and the new, evaluate the important and the unimportant.

Therefore, to be informationally competent, a person must be an active subject of communicative processes. The ultimate goal of mastering information competence is the formation of an active, independent, creative personality, capable of self-awareness and self-expression. The information competence of an individual and the information competence of society are mutually developing and mutually enriching objects. Consequently, the level of information competence of an individual depends on the level of information competence of society, which, in turn, is determined by the information competence of its constituent structures.

Information competence of students includes the following parts that I can highlight:

- necessary for creative solution of professional problems, a set of acquired knowledge;

- a set of different methods of activity necessary for self-realization in professional activities;

- personal qualities of the subject, his needs, motivations aimed at increasing his powers;

- ourselves _ to choose the most important directions , etc.

Scientists T.V. Komar and A.A. Korostelev, who studied the problems of developing information competence of graduate students, showed that it is necessary to include professional information cycles and related concepts in the first year of computer science students. During this period, it is necessary to teach students to use information that will be necessary in the course of their future professional activities.

To achieve this goal, M.I. Bekoeva in her research showed that various electronic publications and resources can be used in the educational process: electronic educational and methodological complexes, electronic textbooks, network educational and methodological complexes. In didactics, students' work with books, reference

books, popular science and educational literature is one of the most important teaching methods. Today we can add fully electronic publications and resources to these resources.

Electronic educational resources in the educational process are divided into basic educational activities used for the direct implementation of the educational process, and organizational aspects used in organizing the educational process.

Key e-learning resources include e-textbooks, e-programs, e-reference books, e-seminars and e-tutorials. We can add to the organizational e-learning resources: curriculum, assessment materials, e-learning materials and initial components to create e-learning resources.

Automated computer programs to increase student interest in the learning process: use of computer network simulation programs such as Arena-Rockwell software, ExtendSim-Imagine Than Inc, Anylogic-XJ Technologies, NetMaker XA, Opnet-OPNET Technologies, Cisco Packet Tracer is a serial [6].

Working with electronic educational resources involves two types of activities: firstly, group work under the guidance of a teacher and consolidation of knowledge, and secondly, independent activity. In both cases, the teacher's task is to satisfy the students' need for knowledge, to convey a wide variety of necessary information that helps consolidate and expand theoretical knowledge.

learning in the process of education Remote filling of resources education resources should also be included. For example, edu.uz, hemis.uz, Moodle.uz, ziyonet.uz and others. In the process of teaching students, the teacher reports the names of sites and gives a brief description of each site.

The use of information and communication technologies in educational practice creates conditions for the formation of cognitive activity and personal qualities in students: independence, creativity, etc., growth, success and self-awareness. Create professional class presentations Finding resources online will help you better understand course materials. Such prepared trainings make it possible to demonstrate interdisciplinarity, acquire theoretical computer skills, activate the mental activity of students, and also encourage them to learn independently [6].

Thus, as a result of the use of information technologies in the educational process, the necessary conditions are created to attract students to knowledge and form the initial competence of students.

In the course of the study, we determined the criteria for the formation of students' information competence. They are :

- 1) the ability to effectively solve issues of one's education and training using information and communication technologies in connection with the emergence of

new, more effective pedagogical tools compatible with the modern information society;

2) the readiness of students to purchase new software in connection with the constant modernization and updating of the educational process;

3) the ability to use information and communication technologies in professional activities.

information competence of students are:

- the ability to search, systematize, assimilate and deliver educational information using information and communication technologies;
- the ability to use advanced capabilities of information and communication technologies when mastering higher education subjects;
- active level of use of information and communication technologies in the educational environment;
- ability to create and maintain a database of educational materials;
- mastering new software products when solving professional problems, as well as increasing their ability to solve functional problems;
- the ability to evaluate the quality and competence of a software product.

The level of information competence of students is determined by the following indicators:

- performing a control task;
- teacher expert score i ;
- survey;
- assessing students' knowledge using a test;
- evaluation of interdisciplinary educational and methodological projects;
- monitor students' performance of laboratory tasks;
- assessment of student's independent work, etc.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, it should be noted that the information competence of students in a broad sense means a person's ability to fully perceive the realities of the information society and use all emerging opportunities, fully adapt to information and self-awareness. Also, on the other hand, the more a person knows how to work with information, the more accessible he is in the information society. League of information competence is a pre-given, defined thing and not by acquiring and developing it to go. This is necessary. A prerequisite for this is high education in the process of appropriate education to adopt it to go. Without using all the educational opportunities that modern information and communication technologies offer us, one can realize that it is impossible to prepare qualified specialists compatible with the rapidly changing reality of life.

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